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CONNECTING SCIENCE WITH SOCIETY

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Minutes of the 5th EU-PolarNet General Assembly

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Minutes of 5th EU-PolarNet General Assembly

Agenda

Conference Date	25th - 26th March 2019
Conference Location	Instituto de Geografia e Ordenamento do Território (IGOT), Universidade de Lisboa
5th EU-PolarNet General Assembly Chairs: Antje Boetius/Nicole Biebow (AWI)	
25th March	
Time:	14:30 -18:00
	<i>Chair: A. Boetius (AWI)</i>
<i>13.30 – 14:20</i>	<i>Lunch</i>
14:30 – 14:45	Welcome by the local host G. Vieira and the project coordinator A. Boetius
14:45 – 15:15	Introduction to the EU-PolarNet Research Programme Development by M.-N. Houssais (CNRS)
15:15 – 16:00	Discussion on the stakeholder issues document as basis of the research programme
<i>16:00– 16:30</i>	<i>Coffee break</i>
16:30 – 17:30	Cont. Discussion on the development of the EU-PolarNet Research Programme (PRP): Content of the chapters, commitments for writing, gaps in expertise etc.
17:30 – 18:30	Meeting of the Consortium - CLOSED
<i>20:00 -</i>	<i>Conference Dinner at Cervejaria TRINDADE</i> R. Nova da Trindade 20 C, 2715-311 Lisbon

26th March	
	<i>Chair: N. Biebow (AWI)</i>
09:00 – 09:15	Agenda for the day and wrap up of the discussions on the Research Programme by N. Biebow (AWI)
09:15 – 09:30	Expectations from the EC and new developments by A. Gambardella (EC)
09:30 – 11:00	Progress report of EU-Arctic Cluster projects: INTAROS by Stein Sandven APPLICATE by Thomas Jung Blue Action by Jens Hesselbjerg Christensen KEPLER by Elaina Ford ARCSAR by Robert Lynch INTERACT by Margareta Johansen ARICE by Veronica Willmott NUNATARYUK by Hugues Lantuit
11:15– 11:45	<i>Coffee break</i>
11:45 – 12:45	WP progress reports and discussion of WP2 deliverables WP1 by N. Biebow (AWI) WP2 by M.-N. Houssais (CNRS) WP3 by B. Schlarb-Ridley (BAS) WP4 by C. Barbante (CNR)
12:45 – 13:00	EU-PolarNet administrative issues – amendment and final report by Tordis Hellmann (AWI)
13:00 – 14:00	<i>Lunch Break</i>
14:00 – 15:00	Discussion of upcoming deliverables: D4.15 White paper on status of stakeholder engagement in polar research by K. Latola (Oulu)
15:00 – 16:00	Discussion of upcoming deliverables D3.7 White paper on European polar infrastructure access and interoperability by G. Vieira (IGOT)
16:00 – 16:30	<i>Coffee break</i>
16:30 – 17:30	Summary of the PRP discussions of day 1: Decisions made, next steps etc.
17:30 – 17:45	Closing of the GA, wrap-up and next steps, N. Biebow (AWI)
17:45 – 18:30	CONSORTIUM ONLY: Information on EU-PolarNet 2

Participants

No.	Surname	Name	Organisation	Country
1	Andersen	Signe Bech	GEUS	Denmark
2	Badhe	Renuka	EPB	The Netherlands
3	Barbante	Carlo	CNR	Italy
4	Beckmann	Katharina	LU	Sweden
5	Biebow	Nicole	AWI	Germany
6	Boetius	Antje	AWI	Germany
7	Cabrita	Maria Teresa	PROPOLAR	Portugal
8	Chappellaz	Jérôme	IPEV	France
9	Christensen	Jens Hesselbjerg	DMI & NORCE	Denmark
10	Dahl	Justiina	SPRS	Sweden
11	David	Ana Salomé Miranda	PROPOLAR / IGOT-ULISBOA	Portugal
12	Dichmann	Frej	UFM	Denmark
13	Ford	Elaina	BAS	UK
14	Franke	Steven	AWI	Germany
15	Gambardella	Attilio	European Commission	Belgium
16	Glowacki	Piotr	IGF PAS	Poland
17	Hellmann	Tordis	AWI	Germany
18	Houssais	Marie-Noelle	CNRS-LOCEAN	France
19	Huybrechts	Philippe	VUB	Belgium
20	Jania	Jacek	CSP	Poland
21	Johansson	Margareta	LundU	Sweden
22	Jung	Thomas	AWI	Germany
23	Lantuit	Hugues	AWI	Germany
24	Latola	Kirsi	UOULU	Finland
25	Lynch	Robert	NMCI	Ireland
26	Macelloni	Giovanni	IFAC-CNR	Italy
27	Mora	Carla	IGOT	Portugal
28	Nolan	Joseph	EPB	The Netherlands
29	Ojeda	Miguel	UTM-CSIC	Spain
30	Ørbæk	Jon Børre	RCN	Norway
31	Pasqualetto	Sara	AWI	Germany
32	Pawlak	Janet	AMAP	Norway
33	Quesada	Antonio	AEI	Spain
34	Sandven	Stein	NERSC	Norway
35	Savela	Hannele	UOULU	Finland
36	Saxinger	Gertrude	APRI	Austria
37	Scheepstra	Annette	RUG	The Netherlands
38	Schlarb-Ridley	Beatrix	BAS	UK
39	Schoener	Wolfgang	APRI/Uni Graz	Austria
40	Scory	Serge	RBINS	Belgium
41	Trifinova	Iglika	BAI	Bulgaria
42	Vaikmäe	Rein	TTÜ	Estonia
43	Valentin	Christine	WOC	UK
44	Velazquez	David	AWI	Germany
45	Vieira	Gonçalo	CEG/IGOT - ULisboa	Portugal
46	Vistad	Rune	RCN	Norway

5th EU-PolarNet General Assembly

Day 1

Chair: Nicole Biebow (AWI)
**Instituto de Geografia e Ordenamento do Território (IGOT),
Universidade de Lisboa**
25th of March 2019
14:30-18:30

1) Welcome words by the local host G. Vieira and the project coordinator A. Boetius

Antje Boetius (AWI) introduces the highlights of EU-PolarNet of the past four years by giving an overview of the main achievements of EU-PolarNet until now:

- Main achievement of **WP 1**: Improvement of cooperation with the EC and between European and International Polar researchers across several disciplines including the cooperation with local and indigenous communities, businesses and other stakeholders.
- Main outcome of **WP 2**: Polar Research for Science and Society are up to now the five white papers, which highlight important research needs from both Polar Regions.
- **WP3**: Infrastructures, Facilities and Data provided the Polar community with an overview of all European infrastructure in the Polar Regions. The European Polar infrastructure catalogue shows which research is possible at the European infrastructures and which facilities are available in the Arctic and Antarctic. It has been developed in close cooperation with the European Polar Board, which hosts also a European Polar Infrastructure Database which evolved from the catalogue and which will be continuously updated.
- Main outcome of **WP 4**: Interaction with Stakeholders and end-users is a stakeholder map and the cooperation with many different stakeholders. Several interactive workshops and online consultations have been organised. Input for the white paper workshop came from more than 500 researchers and stakeholders.
- Other general remarks:
 - Sharing infrastructure is important.
 - Optimisation is important, help scientists to know where to get data.
 - The major task is to connect all components of nature (e.g. climate, sea ice, ecosystems) and society.

Nicole Biebow (AWI) introduces the next two days of the General Assembly:

- Introduction of a remote attendant located in Aarhus (DK) (Søren Rysgaard).
- The agenda of this general assembly is a bit unusual this time because it starts with a half-day discussion. The ordinary general assembly will take place tomorrow with the progress reports from the WPs and several guest presentations.
- Discussion of the research programme:
 - Goal: Find people contributing to the programme.
 - Decide whether we are on the right track.
 - Discuss additional things for the research programme.

2) Introduction to the European Polar Research Programme (EPRP) Development, M.-N. Houssais (CNRS)

WP2 task: Integrated European Polar Research Programme (EPRP) – deliverable due end of November.

- Rationale: EPRP should describe the most important research questions and their societal relevance, co-designed with all relevant stakeholders. Those research questions or needs (as indicated in the draft document) derived from the input of different stakeholders via public consultations and workshops.
- All work packages are involved in the programme. The overall methodology to develop the EPRP included:
 - (1) facilitate a dialogue with all stakeholders, aiming to identify their needs,
 - (2) provide a platform for polar scientist to work together to identify emerging research themes,
 - (3) build on the experience of national and international polar-related bodies,
 - (4) include infrastructure, facilities and data in the consideration and
 - (5) work in collaboration with International organisations and EU funded projects.
- How far are we in the design of the programme?
 1. 10 key polar research themes identified, which have been extracted from the examination of publications of national strategies etc. through a desk study. Identification of topics and linking these topics to key questions and issues; online consultation of scientific community.
 2. Identification of the stakeholder's point of view for polar research issues by a Townhall meeting, stakeholder maps and a continuous dialogue.

Major action: Consultation of all stakeholders on research priorities: “What are the most important topics in relation to your work that should be solved by future polar research?”

3. Co-design of five white papers by researchers and stakeholders. These white papers address a set of core polar research questions.
4. Additional EU-PolarNet products which will be used for the Polar Research Programme are: Inventory and strategic analysis of existing polar observation and modelling programmes, infrastructure catalogue, data management structures and overview of satellite applications
5. At the mid-term retreat the consortiums decided that the white paper should be the basis for the programme, but it should consider issues not addressed in white papers; EPRP should follow a societal approach and start from stakeholders needs to define important research questions; a stakeholder task group was implemented to review the stakeholders' inputs received in EU-PolarNet
6. The methodology was the following: Identification of stakeholder needs by reviewing the stakeholder workshops, online consultations and the white papers and identification of keywords for categorisation -> revised categorisation of stakeholder needs. Outcome: draft of stakeholder issues documents with the following six research needs, sub-topics and underlying issues:
 - a. Understanding of climate change in Polar Regions and link to mid-latitudes
 - b. Informed climate actions
 - c. Safe sustainable and just operations in poles
 - d. Understanding of socio-ecological systems and vulnerabilities

- e. Prosperous living and working in the Polar Regions
- f. Inclusive usage of info and knowledge.
- 7. Implementation of a stakeholder panel of external experts, which reviewed the compilation of the stakeholder needs and is supporting drafting the EPRP.
- 8. An EU-PolarNet working group has started working on the structure of the EPRP: one chapter per overarching theme and prepared a template: introduction, societal relevance of the topics, research questions and finally resources requirements.

To be discussed at this General Assembly: Identification of expertise: we know we have a lot of expertise in the consortium but we most likely need more. We need to build a comprehensive expertise to build the programme.

Action items:

- Update the stakeholder issues document with the results from the last EU-PolarNet workshops.
- Approval of the general template for the EPRP document.
- Writing process needs to be coordinated and contributors need to be engaged.
- Review process has to be defined (who should review, EEAB needs to be involved). The final document has to be circulated within the consortium before it is approved.
- A workshop to finalise the EPRP needs to be organised.

3) Discussion on the stakeholder issues document as basis of the Research programme

- Thomas Jung (AWI): Which period shall programme cover?
 - 5-10 years.
- Attilio Gambardella (EC): We have compiled a list of national projects/programmes for the Arctic Science Ministerial Meeting, which would help in defining research and stakeholder needs. Have you considered this work already? It will be very helpful for drafting the EPRP.
 - Nicole Biebow (AWI): This document was not available when we started to compile the stakeholder needs. Nevertheless, we are aware that several important documents exist like e.g. IPCC etc. and we will consult them. What we have not done up to now is to fill the questions the stakeholders posed on us with life. We have only sorted and structured them because they are heterogeneous. What we still have to do is bringing this into the context of political initiatives and science.
 - Marie-Noelle Houssais (CNRS): This was a bottom up approach. You never get so close to stakeholders at the level of a ministerial meeting, which is also not European but gather different national approaches.
- Hugues Lantuit (AWI) refers to the stakeholder requests: There is going to be a willingness to answer everything they request, but a research programme is not meant to cover everything, it will be difficult to identify link between knowledge and action.
 - Nicole Biebow (AWI): This is true. We have received so many topics. Since we are not writing research papers, but a research programme we try to accommodate as many stakeholder needs as we can but we cannot address all of them.
- Hannele Savela (UOULU): What items does the EC wants to have included in the programme so that it could be the most useful?
 - Attilio Gambardella (EC): A too detailed EPRP could be difficult to use for us since not just one-person works on identifying topics for calls. Under Horizon Europe, this exercise will be even more complex. In addition, we also have to consult the member states. Their reaction would be “this is too difficult to approach” if the EPRP is too detailed.

- Jon B. Ørbæk (RCN): This exercise is fantastic since it is a truly bottom-up approach. One opportunity to value it could be to show the collection of input in an appendix to the EPRP. I agree that this detailed document is not providing coordination in EU polar research; it integrates stakeholder needs but does not help funding agencies and members to identify topics and issues. How is this document going to be used by different actors? If possible, one should do some more prioritisation in order to support the EC and national funding agencies to understand the topics and needs.
 - Attilio Gambardella (EC): As an example, when we have to produce a strategy document at European level, we write a main document which is max 20 pages and then a staff-working document, which can be much longer— consider this as a possible approach.
- Thomas Jung (AWI): With a bottom-up approach, you do not have priorities, but ideas. You need to have a top-down process to end up with priorities. You need a small group to prioritise.
 - Nicole Biebow (AWI): We discussed in the working group how to prioritise, and it is difficult to do it on a European level. We have to do it here where all representatives are sitting and the different expertise is gathered. You cannot put such a prioritisation on the shoulder of a small amount of people.
 - Hugues Lantuit (AWI): Prioritisation means listing a short list of issues and questions.
 - Thomas Jung (AWI): If you do not prioritise you have two options: nobody is going to use it or someone else is going to prioritise and makes other decisions.
- Beatrix Schlarb-Ridley (BAS): You should ask what should be done at the EU level, which research is only possible when different countries are working together, like e.g. investigating tipping points.
- Hugues Lantuit (AWI): There is published work with a framework how to do this prioritisation. The document provides some hints and warnings as to how to frame your points.
- Attilio Gambardella (EC): This document (EPRP) is the start of the process, from our point of view. If you are transparent and clear in explaining how you arrived to the document, it is fine. I cannot say how this will be used, but you need to edit it.
- Jon B. Ørbæk (RCN): It should help to understand where the EC programmes should implement a large action. If we would prioritise, we should identify what topics are already “sold”.
- Marie-Noelle Houssais (CNRS): I have a problem with comparing research and stakeholders’ priorities
 - Antonio Quesada (AEI): Stakeholders are already involved in defining the research questions, we should not go back, and we need to identify the research topics.
- Nicole Biebow (AWI): We received hundreds of research questions, we clustered and prioritised them but we still need to select. Whenever you pose this document to scientists, the reaction would be “where is my topic?” We need a top down approach, but who does it?
 - Hugues Lantuit (AWI): I suggest a framework with ranked questions, which are then considered by a small group and are refined in a workshop. This approach should prevent a “conspiracy theory”.
- Christine Valentin (UK): The research programme has to have a societal relevance. We need to include stakeholders in small groups that prioritise.
- Marie-Noelle Houssais (CNRS): Of course, you need a small group for that.
- Attilio Gambardella (EC): How did you end up with the 6 key topics?
 - Nicole Biebow (AWI): Kristina Bär applied a software (MAXQDA) which sorted themes neutrally. What I liked is what Beatrix Schlarb-Ridley (BAS) said, we should focus on the European perspective: which of these topics can we only approach together? MOSAiC is such an example.

COFFEE BREAK**Cont. Discussion on the development of the EU-PolarNet Research Programme (PRP):**

Discussion on content of the chapters, commitments for writing, gaps in expertise etc.:

Nicole Biebow (AWI) announces a change in the agenda: We will skip the closed stakeholder group meeting and continue in plenary until 6 pm maximum.

She presents the original document and the results of the analysis. Presentation of the methods used to select and process the inputs of the stakeholders:

- Identification of overarching topics, sub-topics and underlying issues, which are by far too many. We decided therefore to skip all the small sub-topics and phrase it in a different way.
- We decided to explain the details of the sub-topics in paragraphs. Nevertheless, we still have a lot research questions and need to cut them down or summarise. Once we fill them with life, the text can be 100 pages. Maybe we should put all questions in an appendix, so that they are not lost. If we deliver such a long and complicated document, nobody will read it.
- Attilio Gambardella (EC): It has to be long; do you have any idea about how many topics we could have for each of the six research themes?
 - Nicole Biebow (AWI): probably up to 10.
- Thomas Jung (AWI): When I see the questions, they are asking for priorities: “What are the key processes?”
 - Nicole Biebow (AWI): That is because we decided to phrase them as questions.
- Jon B. Ørbæk (RCN): We need to try to find a translation between questions and topics. We could have a summary of the previous deliverables but we are trying to make it operational so that it is easy to use. The EC would probably like to see which of those questions are the most important. What one could do is trying to identify those campaigns (MOSAIC e.g.) where one really need the European community to work together and where many of those overarching topics could be addressed.
- Gertrude Saxinger (APRI): The currently formulated items should be the priorities. They reflect the societal needs and derive directly from the diverse activities done by EU PolarNet so far. I could see those things evolving with different methodologies from the stakeholders; there was always this attention to society and societal needs. I think if Attilio said 10 pages as executive summary, we do not have much space and we need to be concise. I like that you have the paragraph, which explains which process has been applied. We need crosscutting procedures to have a stakeholder engagement; many indigenous groups are hesitating in collaborating with research.
- Frej Dichmann (UFM): Within the framework of overarching themes, we can develop key questions. For now, we have a good basis. In a next step, we have to find people who are willing and able to put meat on the bone and make it digestible.
- Nicole Biebow (AWI): EU-PolarNet has done a very good job until now and this is our main deliverable, it has to be a good document as well. My concern is that we should not duplicate the white papers, and for me there is still too much of the white papers in the EPRP, we could even reduce this by extracting what we have in the white papers and take it out, but we would not have a homogeneous programme anymore. What Jon said, if we go for more prioritisation, would be nice but many of stakeholders’ needs would get lost.

- Kirsi Latola (UOULU): I would not worry about duplication; it needs to stand on its own feet. I would not throw anything out; it is so difficult to engage with stakeholders that this could interfere with future collaboration if we do not consider their contribution.
- Annette Scheepstra (RUG): How did you decide to pick what is in the white papers?
 - Attilio Gambardella (EC): The analysis of the landscape of research ended up with 10 topics. External factors (IPCC reports, discussion on climate change) influenced the perception on the importance, we discussed internally and we selected. We had the programme committee. There will be a lot of work that starts from this document, do not worry that it is too much.
- Antonio Quesada (AEI): Our compromise for the white papers was to not lose any of the information we worked on before. We believe that we have all the information already organised and it is here.
- Jon B. Ørbæk (RCN): The document does not include how to operationalise the idea into actions.
- Nicole Biebow (AWI): We will work with Gonzalo on a white paper on infrastructure needs; we will have one on stakeholders' needs and one on data as well. We cannot put all of this in the research programme.
- Frej Dichmann (UFM): We need to take the variability between stakeholder needs and research needs into account; otherwise, we risk making science in the Arctic too complicated.
- Nicole Biebow (AWI): EU-PolarNet is not only Arctic; it is for both Polar Regions. We have to keep in mind that some of the research questions are clearly Arctic and some clearly Antarctic and they need to be equally balanced. In the Antarctic, many questions are research questions in which stakeholders are not involved because people are not so prominent there. We have to keep in mind that we look at all these political initiatives (Arctic ministerial, IPCC, Clean Planet) and see how we can relate them to the research programme. We started to summarise some of the topics into text, and we need people who would contribute and write paragraphs and one or two coordinators for each chapter, we already have one for the socio-economic part (Swedish Polar Research Secretariat).
- Marie-Noelle Houssais (CNRS): Should the coordinators be from within the consortium?
 - Nicole Biebow (AWI): I would prefer within the consortium, but it is not strict.
 - Jon B. Ørbæk (RCN): Contributors need to be acquainted with all the deliverables and issues; it should be scientists writing the research part.
 - Nicole Biebow (AWI): AWI coordinator for the Research Programme, David Velazquez, will send an email listing all the topics asking you to nominate or volunteer. There will be part for which we do not have the expertise here, but maybe in our institutes or organisation. We do not have time for an international nomination process. We will set a short deadline since we will need to react fast. The EPRP needs to be finalised for our Townhall meeting, which will be at the end of November. We are planning a workshop in September in Denmark, where we will sit together and finalise the research programme. What we are expecting from coordinators is to put all the bits and pieces together in a concise chapter.
 - Jon B. Ørbæk (RCN): It is important that the coordinators understand the process of how this work and that the scientist that are going to write the scientific content read all the deliverables.
- Nicole Biebow (AWI): The EPRP should not be written like a scientific paper; I do not see many citations. It should include a chapter that explains why the research is important. We have a tough time schedule, EU-PolarNet ends and we cannot have this extended over the period of the project. I would also like to include the EU Arctic Cluster, where there is a lot of stakeholder and research expertise.

- Annette Scheepstra (RUG): It would be good to have a summary of stakeholder engagement included in the chapter; I refer to Kirsi Latola for that.
- Renuka Badhe (EPB): It would be good to include boxes in the introduction with the overarching themes.

DECISION: The consortium approves the way forward for the work on the research programme.

Nicole Biebow (AWI) closes the assembly for the day

5th EU-PolarNet General Assembly

Day 2

Chair: Nicole Biebow (AWI)
Instituto de Geografia e Ordenamento do Território (IGOT),
Universidade de Lisboa
26th of March 2019
09:00-18:30

1) Agenda for the day and wrap up of the discussions on the Research Programme, Nicole Biebow (AWI)

- The EPRP document is a good basis on which we have to work further. We have to phrase topics better, but we are on the good path.
- Reminds on reacting on the upcoming email for coordinating the writing of the research programme, contributors could be also from institutes, which consortium partners represent.

2) Expectations from the European Commission (EC) and new developments, Attilio Gambardella (EC)

- High expectations, final deliverable to start discussion for the strategic programme of Horizon Europe. Difference to H2020: All services will work together.
- You help a lot to come with good ideas and good requests in terms of topics.
- Arctic Cluster: Participation is voluntary, the meeting that we will have in Brussels in June is to understand the work from last year, but we need to understand how to make the actions of the Arctic Cluster more focussed. We would like to discuss what has been achieved last year in a pragmatic approach, to use the limited resources so that with minimal effort we can have a valuable result.

3) Progress report of EU-Arctic Cluster projects:

The text below summarises only the discussions. All presentations are available [here](https://www.dropbox.com/sh/sozkwnvyt15eqxy/AABj9Q4kw3_S8W3AJMeCcGala?dl=0):
(https://www.dropbox.com/sh/sozkwnvyt15eqxy/AABj9Q4kw3_S8W3AJMeCcGala?dl=0)

3.1) INTAROS by Stein Sandven (NERSC)

Discussion:

- Which connection do you have with Copernicus?
 - Copernicus is more on satellite data and modelling, inclusion of in-situ components depend on contribution from the countries.
- What will happen after end of project with the data catalogue?

- We are working with SAON as a platform for the future.
- Attilio Gambardella (EC): What about sustainability of budget and funding for Arctic observations, are you part of the SAON process?
 - Yes, working on a roadmap.
- Jon B. Ørbæk (RCN): Do you include new platforms and sensors?
 - Some partners are more developers others not. We cannot cover too many of these things, we have to cover a wide range of thematic areas.
- Christine Valentin (WOC): Do you see Artificial Intelligence helping with integration challenges?
 - I do not know, but this certainly is coming up. We need more automatization of data processing.
- Attilio Gambardella (EC): What experience do you have with international cooperation outside H2020? We are asking to improve this cooperation and if you need help from the Commission do not be shy – are you happy?
 - It is going too slowly, we all can work in a traditional way together but you need to find some time to push the process further. Scientists have their challenge with their science, and it is difficult to ask them for more. It would be useful to find drivers to push.

3.2) APPLICATE by Thomas Jung (AWI)

Discussion:

- Jérôme Chappellaz (IPEV): Are you able to isolate processes like polar clouds?
 - This is a model assessment component; we try to understand biases and problems in the model. People like Gunilla Svensson are trying to improve this aspect.

3.3) Blue Action by Jens Hesselbjerg Christensen (DMI & NORCE)

Discussion:

- Annette Scheepstra (RUG): What are your connecting activities?
 - We made ourselves aware; we share our science and results, now we are involved in cooperation especially with APPLICATE.
- Thomas Jung (AWI): We use PAMIP and YOPP especially for cooperation, fair to say that the focus is fundamentally different in certain aspects although there are commonalities
 - Jens H. Christensen (DMI & NORCE): A pragmatic way of collaborating is that we demonstrate that things are not happening aside, but we demonstrate to the funding agencies our results, cooperation but also peculiarities.

3.4) KEPLER by Elaina Ford (BAS)

Discussion:

- A question was asked if we were looking at terrestrial aspects such as permafrost – this is something that is covered by INTERACT (who are linked to KEPLER as Margareta Johansson (ULund) is part of WP1.

3.5) ARCSAR by Robert Lynch (NMCI)

Discussion:

- Antonio Quesada (AEI): Do you cooperate with the SAR system in Antarctica?
 - We share mutual experience; we can learn from them and them from us, we want to engage.
- Jérôme Chappellaz (IPEV): Do you involve insurance companies?
 - We work more with ship operators, but we are engaging with them as well.

3.6) INTERACT by Margareta Johansen (Lund University)

Discussion: None

3.7) ARICE by Veronica Willmott (AWI), substituted by Nicole Biebow (AWI)

Discussion:

- Attilio Gambardella (EC): Any idea on how to engage with Russia, China, Japan, South Korea?
 - AWI has the best possibilities to involve Russia as we have a strong and long-lasting ongoing cooperation. We therefore did many efforts to involve Russia from the beginning on but at the end, the Russians were not able to sort out their administrative tasks for offering one of their vessels in time. We are still in contact with them. We also talked to the PRIC director to involve China. Nevertheless, ARICE is a starting community and since our infrastructure is expensive, we would not be able to add any more partners now.
 - BAS has strong collaborations with South Korea and Japan in the Arctic.

3.8) NUNATARYUK by Hugues Lantuit (AWI)

Discussion: None

4) WP progress reports and discussion of WP2 deliverables

4.1) WP1 – Management of the consortium, International Integration and Policy Guidance, Nicole Biebow (AWI)

- **Task 1.1 Contractual and financial management of the project**
 - An amendment to the EU-PolarNet contract with the EC is currently ongoing, the following administrative changes have been included:
 - **Change in the legal status of beneficiary 10:**
 - Participant 10 (MINECO) has changed to Agencia Estatal de Investigación (AEI), due to a partial takeover, effective since 27 July 2018.
 - **Changes in the team composition of beneficiary 1:**
 - The description of the team of participant 1 (AWI) has been updated due to retirement of the former EU-PolarNet coordinator and AWI director Prof. Karin Lochte. The new AWI director Prof. Antje Boetius has taken over all responsibilities of Prof. Lochte including her role as EU-PolarNet coordinator.
 - **Change of the bank account for payments:**
 - AWI has changed it's bank account starting from 01.01.2019
 - **Changes in deliverables and milestones:**
 - **D1.17:** Third policy briefing in Brussels – **deleted**
 - **D2.11:** Implementation plan for the Integrated Polar Research Programme: deleted, content to be included into **D3.7**

- **D3.9:** Model for a coordinated management system for access and interoperability of European polar infrastructure: deleted content to be included into **D3.7**
- **D3.7: White paper on European polar infrastructure access and interoperability,** broaden the content by an infrastructure implementation plan for the European Polar Research Programme and postpone it from month 40 to month 59
- **New deliverable added: D1.19:** The MOSAiC Example: How to develop and fund a large-scale international initiative from a national bottom-up idea, responsible partner AWI, month 55
- **Postponed deliverables and milestones:**
 - **D1.16:** Minutes of workshop with international partners & stakeholders at SCAR meeting (IPEV) from August 18 to August 19
 - **D2.6:** Roadmap for optimization of monitoring and modelling programs (AMAP) from February 18 to August 19
 - **D3.7:** White paper on European polar infrastructure access and interoperability (IGOT) from June 18 to January 20
 - **D3.8:** White paper on European polar data accessibility (RBINS) from February 19 to November 19
 - **M3:** Second Town Hall Meeting from June 19 to November 19
- **Task 1.2: Operational management, coordination of work package and task leaders, consortium internal communication**
 - Change in the AWI management support team:
 - Kristina Baer left AWI end of 2018 for a position at the Arctic Council in Tromsø.
 - David Velazquez started his work at AWI 1st of March 2019 as EU-PolarNet communication officer.
- **New deliverables since last General Assembly**
 - **D1.13** Policy briefing in Brussels
 - **D1.14** Minutes of Fourth GA incl. at ASSW
 - **D2.5** Strategic analysis of the different monitoring and modelling programs and related infrastructures
 - **D2.7** Second progress report on science - stakeholder Interaction
 - **D2.8** Set of white papers addressing priority questions in polar research and targeting funding agencies and policy makers
 - **D3.6** Gap analysis highlighting the technical and operational requirements of the European Polar Research Program for satellite applications
 - **D4.13** Minutes of stakeholder dialogue at Arctic Frontiers Conference.
- **Task 1.3: Strengthen international cooperation and implement the Transatlantic Research Alliance**
 - **Past events:**
 - Arctic Biodiversity Congress
AMAP/EU-PolarNet Stakeholder Workshop on Research Needs on Arctic Biology and Terrestrial Ecosystems
Date: 12 October 2018
Location: Santa Claus Hotel, Rovaniemi, Finland
 - **Upcoming event:**
 - EU-PolarNet workshop at ATCM-CEP Meeting,
Date: 01. – 11. July 2019, probably 01.07 or 04.07
Location: Prague, Czech Republic
Aim: To discuss societal needs with the Antarctic stakeholders

Format: Evening event (2h), general presentation of EU-PolarNet and the white papers, followed by a round table and debate with the participants.

- **Task 1.4: Evidence-based policy guidance**

- **EU-PolarNet Second Policy Briefing**

Date and time: 26th September 2018, 15:00-17:30

Location: European Parliament, Brussels, Belgium

Theme: “At the frontline of climate change: Key changes in the Polar Regions that call for European action”

Format: Two-hour long policy briefing with EU-PolarNet representatives (A. Boetius & A. Quesada) presenting its five polar white papers and fostering discussions on how European polar research and climate policies can contribute to the protection and sustainable development of the Polar Regions.

Host: Christel Schaldemose, Member of the European Parliament and Chair of the Intergroup’s “Polar Regions”

- **Other events since the last GA**

- **Polar 2018**

Date: 15th - 26th June 2018

Location: Davos, Switzerland

- **Side Event: EU-PolarNet - European Key Research Priorities for Both Poles**

Date: 19th June 2018, 6.30pm – 8.30pm

Presentation of all five white papers incl. panel discussion

Presentation: Co-designing a European Research Programme and the lessons learned along the way in Session: SH-6b Connecting Polar Research Across Boundaries

Date: 21st June 2018, 4.00pm – 5.30pm

- **UArctic Congress 2018**

Date: 3rd - 7th September 2018

Location: Oulu and Helsinki, Finland

Session: The UN Sustainable Development Goals: A signpost for societal relevant polar research?

- Date and Time: 5 September 2018, 10:30-12:00

- Location: University of Oulu

Session: Connecting polar research, policy and stakeholders across scales - examples from Europe and beyond

- Date and Time: 6 September 2018, 10:00-11:30

- Location: University of Oulu

- **Arctic Circle 2018**

Dates: 18th - 21st October 2018

Location: Reykjavik, Iceland

Breakout Session: Research for societal benefit: Where polar research can make a difference

- Date and Time: 19th October 2018, 17:15-18:45, Room Hafnarkot

Breakout Session: And action! Moving beyond benevolent rhetoric in stakeholder engagement

- Date and Time: 20th October, 16:15 - 17:45, Room Skarðsheiði

- Session co-convened with Framsentret, Tromsø

- **EU-Arctic Cluster side event at Arctic Frontiers**

- Improved safety and environmentally sound operations in the Arctic Ocean - how to move forward?

- Date: 23rd January 2019
- Time: 12:30 - 14:00
- Place: Clarion Hotel the Edge, Tromsø

- **Coordination of the EU-Arctic Cluster:**

- Co-organisation of an EU-Arctic Cluster Meeting, 17th April 2018 in Brussels
 - Presentation of the Cluster Task Groups
 - Discussion on future joint activities
 - Updating the website, presentations etc.
 - Co-organisation of the 2nd EU-Arctic Cluster Meeting planned for 4th June in Brussels

Discussion:

- Jon B. Ørbæk (RCN): The Polar research programme needs to be made more operational.
 - Nicole Biebow (AWI): The research programme is due in November and in January the implementation plan, this gives us the possibility to build on research programme. It does not make sense to have three deliverables on same topic; D3.7 will be longer but easier to develop.
- Marie-Noelle Houssais (CNRS-LOCEAN): Could we change the title?
 - No, this deliverable is on the implementation of the infrastructure, which was originally planned. It will show the gaps in infrastructure and give recommendations for improvement. We most likely will not get a lot of new infrastructure but we should work on better coordination and communication. The other implementation part of the EPRP (Int. cooperation etc.) will be a chapter in research programme itself, certainly.

4.2) WP2 - Polar Research for Science and Society, M.-N. Houssais (CNRS)

WP2 objectives

- Identify key polar research questions for Europe through dialogue and cooperation with all relevant stakeholders for the Polar Regions
- Support the coordination and optimization of existing monitoring and modelling programmes and related infrastructures
- Develop an Integrated European Polar Research Programme

WP2 Tasks

- **Task 2.1:** Identification of key polar research questions for Europe (CNR-DTA, RCN, RUG) (M1-M18)
- **Task 2.2:** Development of co-designed White Papers addressing urgent polar research questions (MINECO, NERC-BAS) (M12-M48)
 - Mapping of the key stakeholders (starting with D4.5 with continuous updating), identification of their needs (and engagement), identification of a panel of key stakeholders to be involved in the development of the PRP
 - Meetings and events to exchange information and communicate of EU-PolarNet activities towards stakeholders. The White Paper Workshop was a key event.
 - List of events with objectives and audience in Appendix
- **Task 2.3:** Optimisation of existing monitoring and modelling programmes (AMAP, VUB) (M1-M36)

- The two inventories that from D2.3 are the basis for this analysis.
- Analysis is performed both thematically and spatially to identify gaps in current programmes.
- Information is mapped against the original EU-PolarNet research priorities to determine the extent to which current programmes address these.
- Identification of lacks and gaps, e.g. underrepresentation of human and social sciences, astronomy and space sciences, solid earth interaction, and resource management, underrepresentation of the Antarctic. Additional input from key players and selected sources has been used.
 - → Submitted December, 7th 2018
- **Task 2.4:** Integrated European Polar Research Programme (CNRS, AWI) (M48 -M60)
 - Ongoing actions (EPRP Stakeholder and coordination working groups)
 - Includes stakeholder needs
 - Summary of stakeholder issues based on compilation of existing stakeholder input
 - Nomination of a Stakeholder Panel (following EEAB propositions)
 - Update the map of stakeholder engagement
 - 2. Research Programme Document
 - Template of the PRP document
 - Constitute a group of people to involve in the drafting of the document, checking that we have the needed expertise
 - The whole process should involve the consortium and communities outside the consortium. EEAB used for advice to PRP
 - Ongoing
 - Structure and methodology approved at the 5th GA

Discussion:

- Jon B. Ørbæk (RCN): In the roadmap for optimisation of existing monitoring and modelling programmes some things are underrepresented. It could be sufficient to choose one or two sites for joint research. What is the method of analysis and what thinking is behind optimisation? There are few programmes on astronomy.

4.3) WP3 Infrastructures, Facilities and Data, Beatrix Schlarb-Ridley (UKRI-BAS)

WP3 objectives

- Allow improved joint programming of infrastructure to enable bigger and more complex science
- Main Objective: Improve coordination, optimise use, identify gaps, propose way forward, for:
 - 1) Polar Assets: Design a resource-oriented European infrastructure access and usage plan for the Integrated Polar Research Programme
 - 2) Space Assets: Determine the best approach to wider and more coordinated use of space-based assets
 - 3) Data: Work towards a coordinated European polar research data infrastructure and improve open access to quality controlled data
- **WP3 Task 3.1:** Polar platforms: research ships, stations, aircrafts
 - Work so far

- A catalogue of all existing polar infrastructures (stations, research vessels, aircrafts) – DONE (D3.2, M16, IPEV/IGOT)
 - Identification of polar commercial infrastructures that could be made available to implement the Polar Research Programme – DONE (D3.4, M28, WOC)
 - **Final objectives:**
 - Publish a white paper on European polar infrastructure access and interoperability (D3.7, M40, IGOT-UL)
 - Publish an infrastructure implementation plan for the Polar Research Programme (D3.9, M55, IGOT-UL)
 - Now amalgamated into a single deliverable for M59 (IGOT-UL) that includes both 3.7 and 3.9 and also 2.11 (Implementation plan for the Integrated Polar Research Programme) – to be discussed later on.
- **WP3 Task 3.2: Satellites, communication and remote sensing**
 - Determine the best approach to wider and more coordinated use of space-based assets to support European polar operators
 - Deliverables:
 - D3.3 Survey of existing use of space assets by European polar operators, including recommendations for improved coordination (delivered July 2017)
 - D3.6 Gap analysis highlighting the technical and operational requirements of the European Polar Research Programme for satellite applications and identifying opportunities for improved linkages to ESA and other space agencies (delivered October 2018)
 - **WP3 Task 3.3: Data Management and Interoperability**
 - Pave the way towards a coordinated European Polar Data Infrastructure and improve open access to quality-controlled data
 - Deliverables:
 - D3.1 Survey of the existing polar research data systems and infrastructures, including their architectures, standards/good practice baselines, policies & scopes (M12 – DONE report 1st GA)
 - D3.5 Data management recommendations for polar research data systems and infrastructures in Europe (M32 – DONE – report last GA)
 - D3.8 White paper on how to improve open access to data, interconnection and interoperability of the existing and upcoming polar research data systems and infrastructures (postponed to M57)

Discussion:

Renuka Badhe (EPB): The Polar Infrastructure Catalogue is a great example of a product, which will continue, being relevant after EU-PolarNet and on how to keep the project useful after the end. We have updated the data and it was a big effort but the product is going to produce a very good benefit for the community.

4.4) WP 4 progress report, Carlo Barbante (CNR-DTA)

WP4 – tasks

- **T4.1** Identification of stakeholders: existing and potential (RUG) (M1-M18)
- **T4.2** Identification of stakeholder needs (UOULU) (M14-M54)
- **T4.3** Communication and outreach (NERC-BAS, CSIC) (M1-M60)

Deliverables just approved

- **D4.13:** Minutes of third stakeholder dialogue at Arctic Frontiers Conference

Deliverables in the pipeline

- **D4.14:** Completed stakeholder consultations, report on the needs, gaps and opportunities produced
- **D4.15:** White paper on status of stakeholder engagement in polar research

Timeline:

- Feb-March 15th 2019: EU Arctic Cluster projects are invited to contribute to the White paper, a questionnaire was sent in Feb 21st with deadline March 15th, 2019.
- March 18th – 22nd 2019: Summary from the EU-Arctic cluster projects responses, outline and presentation to be presented and discussed at EU-PolarNet GA in Lisbon
- May – June 2019 - Writing
- July 1st 2019 - White paper finalized

WP4 – tasks

- T4.3 Communication and outreach (NERC-BAS, CSIC) (M1-M60)
 - Focus for 2018: creation of the 'Arctic Cluster Group' to better coordinate communications on big EU-funded Arctic projects. Members include programme managers and communications experts from all 11 projects.

Discussion:

Nicole Biebow (AWI): When we started with writing the proposal and when the project was evaluated, people doubted we could manage the stakeholder engagement. From my perspective, this part went unexpectedly well. We need more time, that is true, but we have to follow up, we are just at the start.

Carlo Barbante (CNR): We reached a large number of stakeholders with continued interaction, and it was the basis for the White Paper.

Jon B. Ørbæk (RCN): The stakeholder mapping is a fantastic job, a huge number of actors. Final analysis, you mentioned a questionnaire – is it going to all the entities listed there?

5) EU-PolarNet administrative issues – amendment and final report, Tordis Hellmann (AWI)

Periodic Report 3

- Due in **September 2019**
- Covering time from **01.03.2018** to **31.08.2019** (18 months)
- Report opens in the Participant Portal on **01.09.2019**
- Consists of:
 - Scientific report
 - Financial report
 - Continuous reporting update

We need information from you to compile these reports and are counting on your support for a timely and correct submission!

- **Each project partner has to fill in their own financial report and send it to the coordinator**
 - You will receive a mail from me in **August 2019**
 - Detailed timeline for the report (stick to it)
 - Guidance on technical issues
 - Examples on what information is needed (stick to it!)
 - Remember: Report will only be open on the 01.09.2019
 - **Keep the dates and stick to the examples given!**

Contact me, I am more than happy to help: Tordis.Hellmann@awi.de

- All **deviations** from the work plan must be explained.
 - Information must be in accordance with the information given in the scientific report!
- **We will need explanations for deviations. Please help us to sort out everything quickly by providing us with this information swiftly, when we ask for them.**
- Please put special attention to this:
 - Travel costs are only eligible when related to EU-PolarNet!
 - You can only claim the costs in the next report when you can proof that they are related to the project.
 - You need to be able to proof each day attendance and the reason for attending > keep Agendas or other means of proof

TIMELINE:

- August 2019 – email with instructions
- September 2019 – deadline for sending report to Coordinator
- September 2019 – check by coordinator and time for clarification of issues
- October 2019 – submission of report
- October to December 2019 – examination by the EU; if needed request for clarifications

FINAL REPORT

- Due in **March 2020**
- Covering the last 6 months but also the whole project time
- (last 6 months from **01.09.2019** to **29.02.2020**)
- Report opens in the Participant Portal on **01.03.2020**
- Consists of:
 - A publishable Summary
 - Technical report – Summary of the whole project, templates and further instructions will be send
 - Financial report – compilation of all periodic financial reports
 - Continuous reporting update
 - Each project partner has to fill in their own financial report and submit it via the participant portal
 - You will receive a mail from me in **February 2020**

TIMELINE:

- February 2020 – email with instructions
- March 2020 – deadline for sending report to Coordinator
- March 2020 – check by coordinator and time for clarification of issues
- April 2020 – submission of report
- April to July 2020 – examination by the EU; if needed request for clarifications
- Payments

Specific rules on payments:

- In total a maximum of **85%** of your Grant amount will be paid out during the project time
- A lot of partners will reach the 85% maximum payment threshold soon or already have reached it
- You will receive your claimed and accepted expenditures together with the Final Payment
- The Guarantee Fund will be transferred separately

Discussion:

Serge Scory (RBINS): If we are above the person month/travel ratio, how can we justify the travel?

Nicole Biebow (AWI): As we do not have sufficient person months, it should be ok to use more funds for travel. Nevertheless, this needs a justification in the technical report. In addition, you need to have documentation in case EU asks for it also years later. We will make sure that there is a relation between final report and technical report.

6) Discussion of upcoming deliverables

D4.15 White paper on status of stakeholder engagement in polar research, Kirsi Latola (UOULU)

The text below summarises only the discussions. All presentations are available here.

The White Paper will include the status of stakeholder engagement, lessons learnt (best practices and failures) and importantly the recommendations for the future research. Not aiming at huge, long white paper – want to make it to the point and concise. The target audience is researchers and funders.

- Attilio Gambardella (EC): This document is more important for the scientific community than for the EC. Do not go to give too many directions. Community engagement: there is still a level of uncertainty in many cases (Canada, Russia, etc.). Will you present this element that in the White Paper or in the handbook for future work?
 - Kirsi Latola (UOULU): It has changed in Europe as well; in North America, for example ethical guidelines have existed quite some time. Ethical review of the research involving people is needed by several countries (like Finland). One of the recommendations is to develop a handbook including all scientific disciplines.
- Annette Scheepstra (RUG): There are different ways to engage, everybody says that we should but we are far from knowing how.
- Nicole Biebow (AWI): What we are doing in EU-PolarNet has an impact on Europe, so one of our huge stakeholders should also be European society. I would start your draft with the question “who is a polar stakeholder and why?” Local and indigenous communities are not our only stakeholders; we have businesses, society, NGOs and policy makers and do not forget researchers. Are we stakeholders as scientists?
- Kirsi Latola (UOULU): We have engaged with indigenous communities and we would need help for the other categories. I’m struggling thinking of researchers as stakeholders in this connection as this is a white paper targeted to researchers on engaging stakeholders, so this is a white paper on how researchers should and could do better stakeholder engagement.

- Annette Scheepstra (RUG): The paper is on stakeholder engagement in Polar Regions, not in EU-PolarNet.
- Jens H. Christensen (DMI & NORCE): It is difficult to see indigenous people in Greenland only as stakeholders, if you refer to them in a white paper, it is important to not make mistakes, be cautious about how you formulate this.
- Renuka Badhe (EPB): Scientists are out of stakeholders, I understand, but in Antarctica you would be cutting out 70% of the community. It needs to be clarified.
 - Kirsi Latola (UOULU): Yes, this will be pointed out clearly in the white paper why researchers are not considered as stakeholders in this particular case.
- Nicole Biebow (AWI): The input comes mainly from the Arctic; we could consider making it from an explicit Arctic focus. We could write acknowledgments about stakeholders in Antarctica.
- Stein Sandven (NERSC): Whom do we represent when we approach the stakeholders?
 - Kirsi Latola (UOULU): You are representing a researcher.
- Renuka Badhe (EPB): In the Stakeholder Board, we have several Antarctic researchers.
- Jérôme Chappellaz (IPEV): States might be the stakeholders there, they are the main stakeholders in Antarctica, and science is the main reason to be a signatory party of Antarctic treaty.
 - Kirsi (Latola (UOULU): Jerome would you like to write about Antarctic states?
 - Jerome: Yes.
- Janet Pawlak (AMAP): If we extend it beyond the EU projects, we can present results on engaging with regional governments.
- Stein Sandven (NERSC): How do you connect or refer to other initiatives (e.g. Copernicus)?
 - Kirsi Latola (UOULU): We reached out to the EU-Arctic Cluster, but where would we draw the line? We have to think about the timeline as well.
 - Annette Scheepstra (RUG): This is a document for future EU projects.
 - Nicole Biebow (AWI): This is a living document; it can only show the present state. If we approach Copernicus, we should do the same with WMO etc. For this White Paper, we can only present a status and what we recommend as EU-PolarNet and the EU-Arctic Cluster. We can write it in the introduction that this is what we have learnt by now. We could use the EU-Arctic Cluster meeting in Brussels to receive inputs in this sense.
 - Kirsi: Yes – agreed, lets use Brussels meeting for more input to the draft paper.
- Attilio Gambardella (EC): When it comes to the review of the draft, are you considering reaching out to some of the indigenous community?
 - Kirsi Latola (UOULU): Yes.
- Nicole Biebow (AWI): Media should be part of it as well.
- Janet: We did not received feedback or answers from media.
- Kirsi (Latola (UOULU): Any volunteers to join to the existing writing team? In terms of Antarctic (Jerome, Renuka, Justiina). Jon and Rune for Arctic joined.
- Renuka Badhe (EPB): EPB could be also partner.
- David Velazquez (AWI): I am in contact with the European director of National Geographic for outreach and communication.

D3.7 White paper on European polar infrastructure access and interoperability, Gonzalo Vieira (IGOT)

- Nicole Biebow (AWI): We need to cut this significantly; we skip for the moment the implementation. We should concentrate on infrastructure interoperability and on how to make it operational.
- One could divide infrastructure e.g. in stations.
- Nicole Biebow (AWI): Instead of listing all out, we could offer our national infrastructure to the international community (e.g. ARICE example etc.). Could we use our White Paper to recommend this as a process? We should use these White Papers as recommendations and say where we see the gaps and where the European community can engage. Access has a lot to do with giving access to our infrastructure to the community and not only to the consortium.
- Jon B. Ørbæk (RCN): We are building on EU-Arctic-Cluster projects; it is quite a large task. In terms of observatories, could we include those lessons learnt there?
 - Jérôme Chappellaz (IPEV): If we could convey the principle of transnational access, I think that should be the way.
- Gonçalo Vieira (IGOT): When we were discussing the catalogue, we decided not to include observatories.
- Nicole Biebow (AWI): We should not go back to infrastructure catalogue, by listing what is there. We have to be strategic, to recommend etc. we have projects working on access at the EU level, we need to make a deliverable that give something strategic saying what needs to be improved, how can it be done etc. I see international cooperation as an important thing.
 - Hannele Savela (UOULU): Not about individual infrastructure, but about concept: how to improve operability and implement those different concepts.
- Miguel Ojeda (UTM-CSIC): We have to clean up our mind and think of another access; we can add new models to access.
- Nicole Biebow (AWI): Portugal and the Netherlands for example, they do not have infrastructure but need access to do research. We, as we have infrastructure, should think about how to make it easier for people like you in accessing and doing research.
- Beatrix Schlarb-Ridley (BAS): Storytelling as a tool to show success, the status now etc. Should we stick to European infrastructure to Europeans or to anyone who want to use it?
 - Nicole Biebow (AWI): We should probably widen it.
- Hannele Savela (UOULU): It is meant to be international it would be artificial to cut it to European team.
- Gonçalo Vieira (IGOT): If we want to improve the impact of the infrastructure, we need to widen the focus and access.
- Jon B. Ørbæk (RCN): Do you include data management and observations in this paper?
 - Nicole Biebow (AWI): Only in terms of observations as physical infrastructures.
- Gonçalo Vieira (IGOT): What is missing is transnational access in Antarctica, and I think it is one of the ways to go forward.
- After this comment, a discussion started on how to develop and implement a transnational access programme similar to INTERACT for the Antarctic.
- Antonio Quesada (AEI): At a European level, it is not as difficult to access the Antarctic stations. We can try to organise and facilitate, as there is no common system, then we could arrange this kind of model and facilitate the transit of people. If we drive an operational model, it would be easier. The problem is that all the access has to go through the national

authorities and the Antarctic treaty authorities. They are clearly identifiable; it should not be too hard; our role could be to ease the access.

- Jérôme Chappellaz (IPEV): The physical access to stations in Antarctica is not the point. The point is that access is governed by national priorities. The way we have people accessing Concordia is through cooperation with Italy or France – but what about the next step?
- Beatrix Schlarb-Ridley (BAS): Focus on education, rules need to be understood from people who want to participate, otherwise they are out and the programme does not work.
- Nicole Biebow (AWI): For the White Paper, should there be a part on Antarctica?
 - Yes, but we should be sure that we recommend something that we can implement.
- Justiina Dahl (SPRS): There should be focus on logistical access, so how to get access to the stations.
 - Gonçalo Vieira (IGOT): We will start to push this through in May.

8) Summary of the PRP discussions of day 1: Decisions made, next steps etc., Nicole Biebow (AWI)

- Six overarching topics have been identified and approved.
- After discussing how and what to prioritize, the structure has been approved, however especially the first chapter has to be re-written, we cannot treat it as finalised.
- We will need volunteers for coordinating and writing the paragraphs and chapters and we need to speed up with these decisions.

9) Closing of the GA, wrap-up and next steps, Nicole Biebow (AWI)

- Last general assembly, made lots of progress in many disciplines but especially in cooperation.
- Still a year to go so not everything is ending now. The consortium grew as a good team and friends, thanks the members for the nice cooperation and support to the management team.
- We will deliver the research programme and deliver nice infrastructure, stakeholder and data white papers.
- Thanks to the Portuguese colleagues for the organization and a present was given as recognition.
- Antonio Quesada (AEI) states, on behalf of the consortium, that EU-PolarNet has been a great European project, everyone worked as team and it has been very successful thanks to Nicole Biebow (AWI).

10) CONSORTIUM ONLY: Information on EU-PolarNet 2

Since this discussion is confidential, no minutes have been taken.